

Human Physiognomy: Why increased accuracies in Face Recognition will trigger the next wave in Rapid Automation

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DIGITAL FACIAL RECOGNITION-BASED INTELLIGENT AUTOMATION SOLUTIONS

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Executive Summary

As it evolves rapidly alongside cloud computing, distributed neural networks, and blockchain, face recognition technology is seeing phenomenal growth in terms of business value and digital maturity.

From biometric cell phone security and building access controls to employee tracking, urban surveillance systems, and fraud detection, face recognition solutions are penetrating every facet of life and can be applied in almost any industry.

Furthermore, [studies have shown](#) that face recognition systems are constantly improving, with most algorithms in 2018 outperforming the most accurate algorithms from a few years prior. The National Institute of Standards and Technology, for example, found a failure rate of only 0.2% when scanning a database of 26.6 million photos. This result was 20 times more accurate than in 2014 when the recorded failure rate was 4%.

In 2019, the global facial recognition market is estimated to hit \$3.2 billion, and through 2024, it is expected to generate revenues of up to \$7 billion, with a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 16%, [according to Mordor Intelligence](#).

While surveillance in the public sector is the biggest driver of this growth, there are numerous other applications supporting that economic advancement in sectors like security, healthcare, and marketing.

In this white paper, we analyze the added value and various applications of face recognition intelligent automation solutions across multiple verticals, painting a compelling picture of the future for organizations that seek to embrace this paradigm-shifting technology.

Additionally, we candidly reveal the strategic planning, experimentation, and product development processes behind HGS's face recognition innovations, detailing the organizational impacts and future business value of these solutions.

Introduction to Face Recognition

Face recognition is a biometric identification system that pinpoints unique features on human faces to match them with existing images. While face recognition is generally accepted as being inferior in accuracy to iris recognition or fingerprint scanning, it is more appealing from a visual standpoint, making it simpler to work with.

Google Photos is one of the many common-use examples of facial recognition in action. The technology behind the platform scans images for faces, then builds models of each face that allow it to group similar images. This approach is similar to most other facial recognition tools in the market today.

How Does Face Recognition Work?

Face recognition software captures, analyses, and compares patterns found on a person's face. It must be capable of detecting faces in images or videos, transforming that information into a digital facial model, then matching that model with other images.

While conventional algorithms focus more on facial features, quality face recognition solutions work by establishing key nodes and landmarks on a set of images using geometric techniques. The challenge is to make these as discernible and unique as possible while maintaining a minimum count to ensure accurate predictions.

What Are the Components of Face Recognition?

When developing a thorough face recognition module with automation at the core, the key components of such a solution should include:

- Image data – metadata (including geodata) extraction.
- Image preprocessing
 - Noise removal via smoothing
 - Trend removal
 - Math processes for pixel operations
 - High-low pass filtering
 - Row-column fits.
- Image works
 - Image editing, segmentation, filtering, transformation, restoration, and image enhancement
 - Image analysis – pattern recognition and edge detection
 - Image exploitation – feature selection, feature extraction, clustering and classification

These lead to the following outcomes:

- Face capturing (analog to digital conversion)
 - Face augmentation (in the absence of varied/diverse/numerous images of the same face)

- Face detection
- Face extraction
- Face recognition (classification) via threshold matching
- Face reconstruction
- Facial expression analysis (emotion analysis)

Industry Applications and Opportunities

The scope of face recognition driven, real-world solutions, and go-to-market products is immense. In assessing the various industrial applications of the technology, HGS was able to identify the following areas as gaps in the market, warranting immediate attention from stakeholders:

- Retail
 - Retail analytics using facial emotions to map consumer interests.
 - CCTV captures to measure footfalls and visit patterns in malls.
- Healthcare
 - Automatic patient identification and scheduling system (for regular check-ups of existing patients)
 - Automatic patient identification and admission system (for emergency check-ins of existing patients)
 - Automatic patient registration and admission systems (for emergency check-ins of new patients)
- BFSI
 - Automatic E-KYC for NRI banking customers through face recognition in combination with OCR-OMR and signature verification tools
- Security
 - Automatic perimeter surveillance and alarm system
- Intelligent Transportation
 - Airports – Automated passenger check-in and automated baggage scanning in combination with OCR-OMR and signature verification tools.
 - Call taxis and railways – Automated passenger face recognition system.
- Local Government
 - Automatic crowd control system during riots and other cases of public nuisance and loitering
 - Face recognition based public ticketing and attendance system in concert halls, theatres, stadiums, etc.
- Schools and Colleges
 - Automatic Student Identification and Attendance Capture System
 - Automatic Student Identification and Academic Record Capture System
 - Automatic Student Identification and Examination Admission System
- Federal Government
 - National Criminal Identification System
- Internal Consumption
 - Visitor Management System for the Admin team
 - Passenger Identification System for the Fleet team

- Employee Attendance Capture System for the HR team
- Employee Access Control and Identification System for the IT team
- Corporate Social Responsibility
 - Tracking missing children in collaboration with NGOs and local police authorities.
- Marketing
 - Using social media images with online activity for tracking and mapping consumer patterns for marketing use - customer segmentation and consumer outreach
 - Using facial images for developing and aligning content on websites
 - Integration with eye-tracking tools to measure content consumption.
- Smart City
 - Traffic violations via speeding, non-payment of tolls, texting while driving, etc.
- Health Monitoring
 - Detect facial moles and lesions and other landmarks and their spread.

The HGS Approach

The combination of recent economic trends, customer feedback, client demand, and HGS's evolving business strategies guided us towards developing data analytics-driven add-ons to existing face recognition solutions.

The added value associated with these commercially viable products became a key focus, as it involved the potential to boost customer satisfaction within legacy engagements, further building on our existing partnerships.

Our initial research indicated that the healthcare and BFSI industries should be primary target areas, as they required extensive data science support for higher quality intelligent automation. Both sectors are experiencing increasing demand for greater accuracy of insurance claims, client/patient records, and customer applications, among others, making them highly suited to face recognition innovations.

How Did We Get Started?

Springboarding off of our preceding work in image analytics, we were easily able to migrate that knowledge and skills over to the development of a standalone face recognition solution. Part of the strategy was to leverage our expertise in neural networks across various other programs while reworking our existing models to specifically train and work with faces, which served to cut down overall development time.

Following a brief brainstorming session, we decided on a modular approach that strictly adhered to the founding principles of preprocessing, QC, and cross-checks. Using open-source platforms like Tensorflow, Keras, OpenCV, and Tesseract, our team was able to work with advanced techniques to design suitable neural network models.

Simultaneously, another group worked on defining potential challenges, researching and selecting new tools, and outlining the appropriate methods for cleaning and preprocessing datasets to make them ready for training and testing.

This modular and concurrent approach enabled us to limit our development cycle to just 10 weeks.

Why In-House Development vs. Off-The-Shelf?

The procurement of commercial off-the-shelf solutions was not part of the ideation process as it was deemed too challenging to integrate them with HGS's existing solutions.

After recognizing that prior machine learning-based image analytics solutions produced quality returns on investment, our clients' upper management teams decided to opt for in-house development.

Our partners were in possession of thousands of images—both employees and visitors—all stored in a disorganized way across several locations in India. By opting for in-house development, the goal was to consolidate these data sets into a single database, with a single platform for accessing, testing, and refining our models.

The data was rich and varied enough to cut across racial and ethnic diversities, which was a treasure trove for us during the model validation stage. It should also be noted that exposing such data to a third-party solution provider would have been fraught with dangers surrounding data security and customer privacy, hence why it was again avoided.

Preparing for Challenges

Following a detailed R&D exercise involving studies of reliability, failures, post-image preprocessing, and image cleaning, the team compiled an exhaustive list of all the things that might constitute a challenge for the final product, including:

-
- Low-level light setting
 - Group images
 - Zoom factor.
 - Red-eye phenomena
 - Viewing and clicking angles
 - Obstructions and background/foreground noise
 - Shadow and glow effects
 - Other radiometric issues like pixelations
 - Facial accessories like tattoos, piercings, beards, ornaments, cloth, etc.
 - Environmental issues like haze, mist, smoke, snow, etc.
 - Camera issues (grainy images from CCTV footage)
 - Drone captures (motion images)
 - A combination of two or more of the above factors.
-

However, the greatest challenge for face recognition platforms is the natural aging of human faces. The process of analysing, comparing, and matching images of people is much more difficult when they are separated by a number of years.

To overcome this hurdle, AI, machine learning, and computer vision systems must learn to estimate how a person might have looked at earlier ages, as well as predict how they might age into the future.

Faced with all of the above issues, HGS took the approach of developing a standard operating procedure (SOP) that ultimately ensured a minimum face detection success rate of 75%, as well as an 80% labeling rate of raw, untrained data. Our ensemble learning mechanism was designed to optimize image routing through a relevant set of algorithms, ultimately detecting and extracting face data from a mix of prevailing noise and lighting conditions.

Image Processing and Neural Networks

Once the images had been passed through preprocessing and cleaning, we looped the following algorithms to ensure a high degree of success in picking out unique faces from the image database:

- Edge detection (Sobel, Canny, and Laplacian)
- Feature extraction (SIFT, SURF, GLOH, HOG, Haar-cascade classifier, and adaptive histogram equalization algorithms)
- Deep neural networks
- Eigenfaces (PCA for linear and t-SME for non-linear)
- Fischer faces (via linear discriminant analysis)
- LPBH (local binary patterns histograms) algorithm

Feature Selection

Original Image

Face Detection

Feature Extraction (Linear)

Cropped Human faces

Eigen Faces

Most Dominant Eigen face

Feature Extraction and Clustering (Non-Linear)

Following successful face detection, the images were passed through an extraction model based on CNN (convoluted neural networks), which maintained the sanctity of the intended areas of interest during the cropping phase—cropping ensures adequate dimensionality reduction to speed up computations.

Subsequent to face extraction, image matching is conventionally achieved via:

- Elastic bunch graph matching
- Template matching
- Contour matching
- Edge matching
- Corner matching
- Support vector machine classifier.
- Probabilistic neural networks using a radial basis function kernel.

A schematic representation of HGS’s proposed approach for a conventional face recognition model is below:

MTCNN: Multi-task Cascaded Convolutional Neural Networks

Analysing the Results

It was observed that while this process was sound, there were recurrent issues with the accuracy of the final output ranging from a low of 8% to a high of 98%.

Face detection and face extraction were a resounding success, under all conditions, while face recognition was an intermittent challenge. The findings were excellent for full-frontal images and images with minimal visual noise, but disappointing in noisy images.

Here we summarize the results from conventional processes:

GIS Image	Facebook Image	Model Output
<p>Model identifies with 95% confidence that the Facebook image belongs to Manasa</p>		

<p>GIS Image</p> <p>Model predicts with 95% confidence that this is Priya</p>		
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<p>Clean Shaven Image</p> <p>Model identifies with 97% confidence that this image belongs to Amit.</p>		
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<p>Group Image</p> <p>Model identifies with 89% confidence that this image belongs to Amit.</p>		
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<p>Red Eye</p> <p>Red Eye Image has been corrected.</p>	
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<p>Childhood Image</p> <p>Model Identifies this Image as Priyanka with 70% accuracy.</p>		
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<p>CCTV Image</p> <p>Model identifies with 91% % confidence that this image belongs to Priya</p>		
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<p>GIS Image</p> <p>Model identifies with 95 % confidence that this image belongs to Priya</p>		
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<p>GIS Image</p> <p>Model identifies with 76% confidence that this image belongs to Priya</p>		
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The HGS Innovation

These initial results were extremely valuable as they helped us modify our SOP. The new approach was as follows:

- Face capture, detection, augmentation, and extraction to continue without adjustments.
- Face detection and extraction to be compounded by the generation of facial landmarks.
- Landmarks and nodes to form the basis of geometric imaging.
- A combination of brute force matching, KNN (k-nearest neighbors) and FLANN (fast library for approximate nearest neighbors) feature matching algorithms to decide percentage match.

Geometric analysis of images involved the use of tessellation, triangulation (distances), translations (rotations and movements), and trilateration (angles) in recognition, classification, and reconstruction. A generalized approach of this is often described as Delaunay triangulation (also known as Voronoi diagrams or Theissen polygons, although there are minor differences in these).

Following this shift, we observed that we were clocking more than a 55% probabilistic match across all face recognition exercises, averaging approximately 88% accuracy across the spectrum, irrespective of noise.

We then attempted facial reconstruction using landmark measurements (distances and angles between the eyes, ears, nose, etc.) up to 128 readings, which also allowed for minor centring of skewed or tilted images.

Below is the corresponding process flow diagram of the proposed solution approach with an enhanced face recognition model.

The results below emphasize the efficiency of geometric imaging in facial recognition, even in the presence of palpable noise:

Train Image	Image with Accessory	Model Output
<p data-bbox="1065 1430 1312 1545">Model identifies with 99% confidence that this image belongs to Chris when analysed via geometric imaging</p>		

Key points (points of interest in the image):

1st image: 50

2nd image: 108

Good matches: 50 (Brute force matching algo, KNN and FLANN feature matching algo.)

How good is the match: **99.91%**

Conclusion: These two faces most likely came from the same person

Train Image	Side face	Model Output
<p data-bbox="1068 548 1317 716">Current model recognizes faces which are tilted away by 30-40° only. A combination of current and side face algos should be able to resolve this. Alternately, we take a shot via geometric imaging.</p>		

LinkedIn Image

Chris Side face Image

Key points (points of interest in the image):

1st image: 98

2nd image: 93

Good matches: 76 (Brute force matching algo, KNN and FLANN feature matching algo.)

How good is the match: **81.72%**

Conclusion: These two faces most likely came from the same person

Train Image	Side face	Model Output
<p data-bbox="1062 548 1308 716">Current model recognizes faces which are tilted away by 30-40° only. A combination of current and side face algos should be able to resolve this. Alternately, we take a shot via geometric imaging.</p>		

LinkedIn Image

Chris Side face Image

Key points (points of interest in the image):

1st image: 98

2nd image: 100

Good matches: 50 (Brute force matching algo, KNN and FLANN feature matching algo.)

How good is the match: **51.02%**

Conclusion: These two faces (marginally) likely came from the same person

Train Image	Zoomed out face	Model Output
<p data-bbox="1068 579 1321 749">Current Model recognizes faces which are closer to the lens and cannot pick faces which are far away (beyond a certain zoom value). Alternately, we take a shot via geometric imaging.</p>		

Chris Image

LinkedIn Image

Extracted Face using DNN

Key points (points of interest in the image):

1st image: 164

2nd image: 11

Good matches: 10 (Brute force matching algo, KNN and FLANN feature matching algo.)

How good is the match: **90.90%**

Conclusion: These two faces most likely came from the same person

Train Image	Group Image	Model Output
<p data-bbox="1040 548 1341 737">Current Model recognizes faces from images which are reasonably well-lit. A Low pass filter applied to such images will transform the brightness/contrast of the image and can then be fed into the model. Alternately, we take a shot via geometric imaging.</p>		

Able to detect two middle faces in the image because of low light effect using Haar-Cascade classifier.

Able to detect three faces in the image using Adaptive Histogram Equalization algorithm.

Able to detect all human faces in the image using Histogram of Oriented Gradients algorithm.

LinkedIn Image

Unknown person's image

Key points (points of interest in the image):

1st image: 164

2nd image: 4

Good matches: 0 (Brute force matching algo, KNN and FLANN feature matching algo.)

How good is the match: 0%

Conclusion: These two faces most likely came from different people

LinkedIn
Image

Unknown person's
image

Key points (points of interest in the image):

1st image: 164

2nd image: 21

Good matches: 5 (Brute force matching algo, KNN and FLANN feature matching algo.)

How good is the match: **23.80%**

Conclusion: These two faces most likely came from different people

LinkedIn
Image

Unknown person's
image

Key points (points of interest in the image):

1st image: 164

2nd image: 11

Good matches: 1 (Brute force matching algo, KNN and FLANN feature matching algo.)

How good is the match: **9.09%**

Conclusion: These two faces most likely came from different people

LinkedIn Image

Unknown person's image

Key points (points of interest in the image):

1st image: 164

2nd image: 51

Good matches: 50 (Brute force matching algo, KNN and FLANN feature matching algo.)

How good is the match: **98.03%**

Conclusion: These two faces most likely came from the same person

Train Image	Group Image	Model Output
<p>Current face extractor model does not pick out any faces from this picture due to zoom effects coupled with background brightness and noise. An alternate face extractor model can be used to decipher faces, which in turn, can be fed into the current model. Alternately, we take a shot via geometric imaging.</p>		

Detection and Extraction of faces in a group image

Crop and save individual image

LinkedIn Image

Unknown person's image

Key points (points of interest in the image):

1st image: 164

2nd image: 58

Good matches: 20 (Brute force matching algo, KNN and FLANN feature matching algo.)

How good is the match: **34.48%**

Conclusion: These two faces most likely came from different people

LinkedIn Image

Unknown person's image

Key points (points of interest in the image):

1st image: 164

2nd image: 86

Good matches: 37 (Brute force matching algo, KNN and FLANN feature matching algo.)

How good is the match: **43.02%**

Conclusion: These two faces most likely came from different people

LinkedIn Image

Unknown person's image

Key points (points of interest in the image):

1st image: 164

2nd image: 105

Good matches: 30 (Brute force matching algo, KNN and FLANN feature matching algo.)

How good is the match: **28.57%**

Conclusion: These two faces most likely came from different people

LinkedIn Image

Unknown person's image

Key points (points of interest in the image):

1st image: 164

2nd image: 63

Good matches: 27 (Brute force matching algo, KNN and FLANN feature matching algo.)

How good is the match: **42.85%**

Conclusion: These two faces most likely came from different people

LinkedIn Image

Unknown person's image

Key points (points of interest in the image):

1st image: 164

2nd image: 67

Good matches: 65 (Brute force matching algo, KNN and FLANN feature matching algo.)

How good is the match: **97.01%**

Conclusion: These two faces most likely came from the same person

Designing a Business Frontend and GUI

With positive results confirming that we had an effective face recognition platform, it was time to get the application into production.

We started by designing a primitive user interface and introducing an exhaustive training and testing process to assess the computational efficiencies of our team. We also provided our team with seamless access across hosting servers while having the means to measure latency, establish the platform’s ease of use, and ensure the face recognition-based visitor management system was visually appealing.

As seen below, this progress output sample vouches for the accuracy of the program:

Below is a comprehensive solution architecture planned for the application’s design, which invokes the facial recognition engine and constructs optimal processes for a large-scale project.

Covering all facial recognition exercises, a corresponding and generic solution approach is seen below:

Cost Limitation Practices

The presence of our own existing models, datasets, and techniques allowed for low development costs with no additional charges projected for the future. Through the use of optimal computing and coding methods, we were also able to cut down on resource-intensive, time-consuming processes, negating any need for additional hardware and computing resources.

Where available, we allowed for distributed computing and parallel processing, which ensured a latency of five seconds or less. We are also making a continuous effort to improve the accuracy metrics and cut down on the output time, supported by the self-validation of models built throughout our approach and cross-validation with open-source models.

Projected Return on Investment

Given the low development investment, ROI will start off positive. Our in-house development approach allows us to save on data, infrastructure, and external vendor support as we build new intellectual property in this space.

Additionally, by automating internal operations that traditionally rely on manual identification, across HR, fleet, information security, and administration departments, we project cost savings of up to 50% for our clients, as well as a tenfold reduction in processing times in each department. Most of these cost savings would stem from the reduction in manual operations and the retiring of redundant solutions or infrastructure.

Following implementation, our clients within the BFSI and healthcare spaces will provide HGS a service-based royalty for the use of our IP, as well as covering the billable man-hours related to R&D.

HGS's existing facilities and clientele in India will serve as launch pads for future innovations in the face recognition space, with the initial deployment phase bringing in customer engagements in excess of 10 million INR (US\$141,000), which represents a substantial ROI for the Indian market. As we mature as a service provider, we hope to scale those numbers year-on-year.

Defining the Ideal Pricing Model

A trade-off between the number of images available, levels of accuracy required, and the time of processing would be the deciding factor in establishing pricing bands for this solution.

For example, a BFSI company would need a face recognition solution with a high degree of accuracy, given the financial records at stake, but could accommodate low levels of lag. Comparatively, an office reception desk that issues entry permits, or parking authorizations would require minimal levels of accuracy but faster processing speeds.

Given that end-users are consuming the output in diverse ways, we have outlined a price governance model accordingly, tailor-made and customized for different industry verticals:

Potential Use Cases

As mentioned earlier, face recognition is not error-proof, nor is it as accurate as iris scanning or fingerprint matching, so due diligence is a must when it comes to accepting photo matches as evidence, for example. At best, facial recognition in critical areas like scene reconstruction or forensics should be suggestive in nature, leading to higher-level investigations.

In the context of privacy, face recognition should ensure a more defining argument in the security of individuals' details, while also providing a means to leverage various automation services.

The patient admission and scheduling system for hospitals has been a standout use case for HGS. One of our solutions in development promises to cut waiting times during scheduled check-ups by 66%, as well as identifying known patients in under three seconds and alerting police stations of unknown faces in emergency situations in under one minute.

HGS - Future in Face Recognition

Encouraged by the results of this innovation, HGS has set a plan in motion to commercialize and productize excellent in-house face recognition solutions. We currently have one going into production, two in the design phase, and another in the proof-of-concept stage.

The next step is to deploy our omni-faceted solutions at leading businesses in India, Philippines, Jamaica, USA, and the UK through a multi-pronged strategy:

1. Employ internal deployments as launch pads for technology acceptance and endorsement.
2. Collect UAT reports specifying metrics for business approval and validation, including:
 - a. ease of use and user-friendliness
 - b. reduction in computational times
 - c. latency
 - d. visual appeal
3. Vet our findings for a second opinion and accuracy checks from concerned teams – Fleet, HR, Info Security, Travel desk and Admin.
4. Source as many labeled data sets as possible to train and refine our models to better our accuracy metrics.
 - a. The labeled data would come from internal sources.
5. Help advertise our services to potential external clients aided by business development, sales, and pre-sales teams.

The Value Addition – Integration with Geoanalytics

At HGS, we see the next disruptive innovation in face recognition employing geo-analytical support using advanced geographic information systems.

Within the security and law enforcement sectors, combining geo-information with face recognition solutions could result in the following use cases:

- Use a patrolling police officer's camera to geotag potential suspects when the image is captured.
 - Extend that functionality to CCTV footage, drone captures, or toll booth infrared cameras.
- Extract geo-coordinates embedded in images.
- Use a cell phone's built-in GPS system for tracking suspects.
- Use cell phone tower-based triangulation system to narrow down the location of a person of interest.
- Use a computer's location information.
- Use open-source information detailing suspect location.

Some of the potential use cases identified for HGS's roadmap include:

- Use GPS routing to predict a suspect's potential exit points or destinations.
- Use geo-fencing to raise early warning alarms for a suspect's potential violation of no-go areas.

- Use device location information to spatially correlate web purchasing patterns, web crawls, internet use, walk through a retail store, etc., with a face or a demographic.
- Develop a crime analytics model with a temporal analysis of the suspect's movements.

Improving Accuracy in Face Recognition and Expression Analysis

Recent technological advancements related to the finite element method (FEM) are expected to boost the reliability and value of face recognition technology, representing an exciting step forward in this area of intelligent automation.

FEM is a mathematical approach to solving partial differential equations by localizing content or dissolving larger entities into smaller components. The corresponding analysis is called finite element analysis (FEA).

With FEM, it is possible to design a unique data structure that could accurately depict and represent various facial anatomical features, advancing ahead of the facial nodes and landmarks analysed by the standard solutions. There is also the possibility to develop a finite element-based mesh structure and perform similarity metrics-based face matching via SIFT and SURF algorithms.

In light of these advancements, the next logical step would be to research the impacts that a finite element-based algorithm could have on the analysis of geometric patterns caused by facial deformations, or during periods of physiognomic expressions. New technology for analysing emotion and intent in human facial expressions is also in development.

Our preliminary investigations into FEM models reveal encouraging results. While Delaunay triangulation could at best work with sample sizes of just 128 geometric components or key points, the FEM approach—while being more computationally intensive—allows us to potentially work with upwards of 8,000 by reducing polygons to their granular sub-components. Some of these results are summarised below.

Face Mesh

Original Image

Mask Image

Landmark detection Image

Outer geometry of Image

Geometry of Image

Similarity Match using SIFT Algo

Keypoints 1ST Image: 438

Keypoints 2ND Image: 8765

GOOD Matches: 351

How good it's the match: 80.13698630136986

Image Hash

Comparison	Similarity Score of Image Hash in Percentage			
	Average Hash	Perceptive Hash	Difference Hash	Wavelet Hash
Image 1 & 2	80.01	89.0	68.12	78.12
Image 1 & 3	62.12	59.37	65.18	68.75
Image 1 & 4	43.99	48.25	53.12	50.0
Time (in Sec)	0.04	0.07	0.04	0.12

Note:
 Image 1 : aradhana1.jpg
 Image 2 : aradhana2.jpg
 Image 3 : manasa.jpg
 Image 4 : chris.jpg

Similarity match using Image Hash

	Similarity Score (%)	Response Time
Image1 & Image2	62.5	0.09
Image1 & unknown Image	50.0	0.09
Image1 & Image3	75.0	0.09

HGS Data Sciences unit developed face mining solution stands-out in this regard with its abilities in:

- Thorough data cleansing and preprocessing in the signal space
- Seamless on-site deployment
 - Accurate isolation and labeling of discernible patterns
 - Robust anomaly and outlier detections
 - User-friendly GUI based controls.
 - High standards of security and privacy
- Developing and listing editable, trainable and customizable libraries
 - Unhindered access to statistical models driven by in-house designs.
 - Fine-tuning weights and parameters of various ML libraries based on automatic error minimization.
 - A comprehensive evaluation of models on 100s of imaging data sets for facial recognition
 - Custom hybrid modeling leveraging expertise from transfer learning modules.
- Being computational optimized and cost moderate
- Operationally friendly based on feedback received in UAT reports.
- Periodic updating and upgrading and keeping abreast of the latest advances in ML and AI technologies.

About HGS

HGS is a marketing, data science, and technology consulting and services provider that has helped various teams within 100+ organizations with digital transformation and automation solutions. Through our data-driven services, we help customers select the right models and systems and implement a complete strategy that helps teams get higher ROI out of their existing investments.

Our Data Practice has a matured and diverse portfolio, supported by big data experts who help clients successfully strategize and implement data-driven solutions within their organization. By integrating the right data from different systems, we help clients understand their customers better. Through AI- and ML-based data modeling, analysis, reporting, and visualization, we are able to provide our clients with timely and highly valuable and actionable insights.

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